

Effect of acrylic acid doping on the properties of chemically synthesized polyaniline

P. Chowdhury*, B. Saha, B. Singha, S. Ghosh and I. Basumallic

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235, West Bengal, India

E-mail : pranesh_02@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 6 August 2006, accepted 4 December 2006

Abstract : Polyaniline (PANI) doped with acrylic acid (AA) was synthesized by chemical method using potassium dichromate as oxidant. The AA doped PANI was found to be more soluble in organic solvents (*m*-cresol, *N*-methyl pyrrolidone) than that of HCl doped PANI. The co-doping of AA and HCl with PANI in a particular mole ratio (HCl : AA = 7 : 1) showed higher conductivity than individual dopant. Spectroscopic properties (FTIR, UV-Vis) and thermal stability (TGA) of the doped PANI have been studied. The inhibitory effect of the AA doped PANI on the corrosion of iron rod has been investigated by using open-circuit potential (OCP) measurement and electrochemical polarization method.

Keywords : Polyaniline, acrylic acid doping, conductivity, corrosion inhibition.

Polyaniline (PANI) is a polymer that displays a wide spectrum of applications¹. The PANI has been doped with various organic acids to make it soluble in organic solvents and aqueous medium². PANI has corrosion inhibition property also³. We observed that hydrochloric acid doped PANI has poor adhesion on the iron surface⁴. As a result, HCl doped PANI could not be used as such for protection of iron. A modification of the material is required to improve its adhesion property. There is enough scope for further research work to improve its conductivity, yield, thermal stability and erosion inhibition properties.

In the present work, we report the effect of acrylic acid doping and co-doping on the properties of chemically synthesized PANI using potassium dichromate as an oxidant. The results are explained in relation to HCl doped PANI. Effects of organic solvents on the polymer properties are discussed. The erosion inhibition property of the AA has been studied.

Experimental

Materials : Aniline (A) (Merck, India) was purified by distillation over zinc dust. The middle fraction of the distillate was collected and stored in a refrigerator. Potassium dichromate (Pfizer Ltd., India), sodium chloride (Merck, India), acrylic acid (AA, Sisco, India), *m*-cresol (Qualigens, India), *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) (Sisco Research Laboratory Pvt. Ltd., India) was used as received.

The polymerization was carried out in a three-necked round bottom flask that was kept at constant temperature

(0 °C) ice bath. 2.2 mL aniline (0.024 mol) was taken in the flask with required distilled water, concentrated hydrochloric acid and acrylic acid (formulation of different sets are given in Table 1). After homogeneous mixing by a magnetic stirrer, 25 mL 0.4 M K₂Cr₂O₇ solution (0.01 mol K₂Cr₂O₇) was added to the reaction mixture. Total volume of the reaction mixture was kept at 100 mL. Nitrogen atmosphere was maintained throughout the reaction period. After 4 h, the precipitated polyaniline salt was filtered and then washed with distilled water until the washing liquid was completely colorless. The material was dried at room temperature for 48 h in a dynamic vacuum until constant mass was reached.

The electrical conductivity of the samples was measured by a standard four probes method at room temperature⁴. Hardness of the pellets (pellets were prepared by a hydraulic press) was measured by a durometer. FTIR spectrum was recorded on a Shimadzu (Model No. 84005) FTIR system in the range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹ using KBr pellets. UV-Vis spectra of the sample solution in NMP were recorded using Shimadzu UV-Vis-NIR (UV-3101 PC) spectrophotometer. Thermal degradation studies were performed under nitrogen gas atmosphere using Shimadzu DT-30 at a linear heating rate of 10 °C/min from room temperature to 500 °C⁵. The flow time of the PANI salts were determined at 27 °C using an Ubbelohde viscometer. The 0.1% solution of PANI in concentrated H₂SO₄ was used for this purpose.

Corrosion studies : The electrochemical experiments were performed in 3% NaCl solution using three electrodes

configuration. The iron rod (8 mm diameter) was used as the working electrode. A platinum foil (1 cm²) and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) were used as counter and reference electrode, respectively. The polarization measurements were performed by sweeping the potential between -250 mV and +250 mV with the help of open circuit potentiometer (OCP) at the scan rate of 2 mV/s.

Results and discussion

Effect of acrylic acid doping :

The effect of acrylic acid doping on the properties of PANI is shown in Table 1. The sample PANI-1(HCl doped) that is prepared from 2.4 M HCl solution showed conductivity in the order of 2.6 S/cm with high yield⁴ as observed earlier by some workers⁶. However, Athawle *et al.* got much lower conductivity of HCl doped PANI⁷. The addition of small amount of AA with HCl (HCl : AA

polymers increases with the increase of acrylic acid content. This is probably due to increase of molecular mass of the resulted polymer in the presence of acrylic acid.

The FTIR spectra of acrylic acid doped PANI (PANI-4) and HCl doped PANI (PANI-1) is shown in Fig. 1 and peak position related to the corresponding chemical bonds with references are listed in Table 2. A significant difference between the two spectra is observed. The spectrum of AA doped PANI shows two bands at 1158 and 1705 cm⁻¹, which are absent in the spectrum of HCl doped PANI. The peaks at 1158 and 1705 cm⁻¹, may be assigned as the vibration of the dopant acrylate anion and carbonyl-stretching band of saturated carboxylic acid⁹ respectively. The presence of these peaks confirms the doping of AA with PANI. The peak assignment in Table 2 suggests that both PANI-1 and PANI-2 are polyaniline.

Table 1. Effect of acrylic acid

Sample	HCl (mol/dL)	AA (mol/dL)	Mole ratio HCl : AA	Color	Yield (%)	Conductivity (S/cm)	Hardness (shore A)	Solubility (%) in <i>m</i> -cresol	Solubility (%) in NMP	Flow time (s)
PANI-1	0.24	-	Infinity	Green	95.69	2.60	80	20	15	122
PANI-2	0.21	0.03	7 : 1	Green	94.51	6.50	76	65	55	124
PANI-3	0.18	0.06	3 : 1	Light green	86.70	6.1 × 10 ⁻¹	71	70	61	127
PANI-4	-	0.24	0	Light green	56.10	3.8 × 10 ⁻³	61	90	82	131

= 7 : 1, mole ratio) produce co-doped PANI (PANI-2). PANI-2 exhibited higher conductivity than PANI-1. The higher conductivity of PANI-2 is probably due to higher degree of doping. Similar type of enhanced conductivity (synergistic effect) due to doping of AA was observed by them. The conductivity obtained by them (6.2 × 10⁻³ S/cm) is much less than the present study (6.50 S/cm). The higher conductivity of the current study may be due to difference in synthesis conditions and oxidant. The presence of AA in PANI-2 improves its solubility in organic solvents (*m*-cresol and NMP). The introduction of AA with HCl in the mole ratio 3 : 1 (PANI-3) gave rise to both lower yield and conductivity. No synergistic effect occurred in this mole ratio. The system without HCl (PANI-4) provided further lower yield and conductivity because acrylic acid itself acts as a pseudo protonic acid dopant. PANI-4 was found to be much more soluble in organic solvents. Gradual replacement of HCl dopant by AA lowers the hardness of the resulted polymers. The color of the samples reveals that the resulted polymers are emeraldine salt form of PANI⁸. Lightness of color for the samples PANI-3 and PANI-4 is probably due to lower degree of protonation. The flow time of the

The UV-Vis spectra of PANI (PANI-1, 2, 4) in NMP solution are shown in Fig. 2. Spectrum (□) represents HCl doped PANI (PANI-1), spectrum (○) stands for AA doped PANI (PANI-4) and that of (∇) denotes HCl/AA co-doped PANI (PANI-2). All the spectra show two absorption maxima at 330 and 630 nm. The λ_{max} at 330 nm corresponds to the π-π* transition of the benzene ring and broad absorption peak at 630 nm is due to n-π* transition of the non-bonding lone pair electron on nitrogen atom. The spectra (○) shows higher absorption than that of (□) in the range 300 to 900 nm indicating higher

Table 2. FTIR bands (cm⁻¹) of HCl and AA doped PANI^{7,8}

PANI-1 (HCl doped) cm ⁻¹	PANI-4 (AA doped) cm ⁻¹	Peak assignment
810 (sharp)	795 (sharp)	<i>Para</i> disubstituted benzene ring
-	1158 (strong)	Vibration of the doped anion
1290 (sharp)	1291 (sharp)	C-N stretching bond
1480 (intense)	1479 (intense)	Benzene ring stretching band
1560 (shoulder)	1556 (shoulder)	Quinoid ring stretching band
-	1705 (broad)	Saturated carboxylic acid band
2505 (medium)	2505 (medium)	NH ⁺ stretching band

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of (a) HCl doped polyaniline, (b) acrylic acid doped polyaniline.

solubility of PANI-4 than PANI-1 in NMP. The spectrum (∇) exhibits more absorption than both the spectra (□) and (○) in the range 800–900 nm. The presence of the broad band at higher wavelength represents the extended coil conformation with higher degree of protonation².

Thermal analysis :

The thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA) curve of the

samples PANI-1 (HCl doped) and PANI-2 (AA co-doped) are shown in Fig. 3. The sample PANI-1 shows two-stage weight loss whereas the sample PANI-2 exhibits three-stage weight loss. The first stage mass loss of PANI-1 (from 50–180 °C) is due to loss of moisture. The second stage weight loss starts at 350 °C and continues up to 500 °C. This may be attributed to oxidative degradation of

Fig. 2. UV-Vis spectra of PANI in NMP solution : (□) HCl doped (PANI-1), (○) AA doped (PANI-4), (∇) HCl/AA co-doped (PANI-2).

Fig. 3. TGA curve of (□) HCl doped PANI-1, (○) HCl/AA co-doped PANI-2.

the polymer. Similarly, the three stage mass loss of the grafted product may be explained as a loss of moisture, oxidative degradation of PANI and decomposition of polyacrylate chain respectively.

Corrosion inhibition behavior :

Fig. 4 shows the open-circuit potential (OCP) of the PANI-4 (AA doped PANI) coated iron rod in 3% NaCl solution as a function of the time. The horizontal line at -628 mV vs SCE (Saturated Control Electrode) is the corrosion potential of bare iron rod. The OCP of the coated sample is more positive than that of bare sample by 149 mV and it was fairly constant over long period. This indicates the protection of the coated sample against

Table 3. Potentiodynamic polarization measurement results

Sample	E_{corr} (mV)	I_{corr} (μ A)	Ca (β) (mV)	An (β) (mV)	Cor. rate (mpy)
Bare Fe	-643.00	46.790	260.75	76.35	88.33
Coated Fe	-441.977	6.177	154.07	34.40	11.65

clear from the table that the E_{corr} and I_{corr} are lower than the corresponding bare sample. The I_{corr} decreases from 46.79 μ A to 6.177 μ A and the E_{corr} increases from -628 to -441.977 mV for the coated sample. From these results, it can be concluded that the AA doped PANI has good inhibitory properties towards corrosion of iron rod in 3% NaCl solutions. The Tafel's plot of coated samples has

Fig. 4. Plot of open circuit potential of AA doped PAN coated Fe-rod in 3% NaCl solution versus time.

corrosion in 3% NaCl solution³. The polarization experiment (Tafel's plot) in 3% NaCl is shown in Fig. 5. The E_{corr} , I_{corr} , corrosion rate, cathodic and anodic bea, obtained from the curves, are tabulated in Table 3. It is

also been recorded after storing it for 7 days in air at room temperature and the curve is overlapped with the initial data, as shown in Fig. 6. These curves clearly indicate that there is no substantial loss in the corrosion

Fig. 5. Tafel plot for (a) bare, (b) AA doped PAN coated Fe-rod in 3% NaCl solution.

Fig. 6. Tafel plot for AA doped PAN coated Fe-rod (a) freshly prepared and (b) after storage in air for 7 days at room temperature recorded in 3% NaCl solution.

protective properties of the AA doped PANI samples. It is also interesting to see the effect over a long period, which is under investigation. The samples PANI-1, PANI-2 and PANI-3 were found to be very low corrosion inhibition properties due to their low adhesion ability with iron rod.

Conclusion :

The acrylic acid doped PANI is highly soluble in organic solvents like *m*-cresol and *N*-methyl pyrrolidone and it has fairly good corrosion inhibition property. The co-doped PANI (HCl : AA = 7 : 1 mole ratio) has higher conductivity than singly doped PANI due to higher degree of protonation. The corrosion protective properties of the modified PANI retained after storing it in air for more than 7 days and hence it can be a potential coating material for corrosion protection of iron or stainless steel in 3% NaCl solution.

References

1. E. M. Genies, A. Boyle, M. Lapkowschi and C. Tsintavis, *Synthetic Metals*, 1990, **36**, 139; M. V. Kulkarni, A. K. Viswanath, R. Marinuthu and J. Seth, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A : Polymer Chemistry*, 2004, **42**, 2043; M. Gazard and Skotheim (ed.), "Handbook of Conducting Polymers", Marcel Deker, New York, 1986, Vol. 1, Chap. 19; C. Arbizzani, M. Mastragostino and B. Scrosati, "Handbook of Organic Conductive Polymer", ed. H. S. Nalwa, Wiley, New York, 1997, Vol. 4, Chap. 11; T. L. A. Campos, D. F. Kersting and C. A. Ferreira, *Surface and Coating Technology*, 1999, **122**, 3.
2. J. Iaska, J. Widlarz and E. Wozny, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A : Polymer Chemistry*, 2002, **40**, 3562.
3. V. Shinde, S. R. Sainkar and P. P. Patil, *Trans. SAEST*, 2005, **40**, 81; K. Hnini, A. Chataini and A. Elbouadili, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 2004, **20**, 481; A. Subramania, N. T. Kalyana, P. R. S. Sundaram, V. S. Muralidharan and T. Vasudevan, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 2004, **20**, 49.
4. P. Chowdhury, B. Saha, P. Ghosh, A. Sankar, M. Ghosh, A. K. Meikap and S. K. Chatterjee, *Czech. Slovak. J. Phys.*, 2003, **53**, 1219; P. Chowdhury and B. Saha, *Ind. J. Chem. Technol.*, 2005, **12**, 671; *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, (in press).
5. P. Chowdhury and A. Ali, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 2005, **22**, 277.
6. Y. Cao, A. Andretta, A. J. Hegger and P. Smith, *Polymer*, 1989, **30**, 2805; M. A. Rodrigues and M. A. D. Paoli, *Synthetic Metals*, 1991, **41-43**, 2957.
7. A. A. Athawle, M. V. Kulkarni and V. V. Chabukswar, *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 2002, **73**, 106.
8. J. Stejskal, M. Spirkova, A. Riede, M. Helmstedt, P. Mokreva and J. Prokes, *Polymer*, 1999, **40**, 2487; B. M. Mandal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 121; E. Marie, R. Rothe, M. Antonietti and K. Land Fester, *Macromolecules*, 2003, **36**, 3967; A. Gok and B. Sari, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2002, **84**, 1993.
9. J. R. Dyer, "Application Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 1991, p. 36; D. H. William and I. Fleming, "Spectroscopic Methods in Organic Chemistry", 4th ed., Tata McGraw-Hill Publication, New Delhi, 1988, p. 50.